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Educational Inequality in India & Vision of NEP- 2020 for Equitable and Inclusive Education

Monica Awasthi

Assistant Professor,
A P Sen Memorial Girls' PG College Lucknow,
University of Lucknow
mmonica.ggic@gmail.com

Abstract

The 20th century served as the foundation for the modern individual. The three areas that require the most attention are diet, healthcare, and education. Education is a fundamental human right that has a significant impact on individual lives and societies. However, in India, educational inequalities persist, hindering the nation's overall growth and development. Despite considerable progress made in recent years, India is still home to many people deprived of educational opportunities. Educational inequality is the unequal distribution of academic resources (human and non-human resources) including school funding, qualified and experienced teachers, books and technology to socially excluded community. Educational inequality between white and minority students continues to perpetuate social and economic inequality. It converts further into the inequality of opportunity. Inequality of opportunity occurs when people living in same society do not have access to same opportunities. India, the most populous country of the world is also a nation with a rapidly expanding population. No doubt India has the potential to become a world powerhouse in the next few decades. But for this, the people of India must have the knowledge required to drive and power it towards becoming a true global powerhouse. People's education is impacted by their social, political, and economic circumstances. Rich people are frequently given the chance to enroll in top universities and other educational institutions. Even though those from lower socio-economic groups are more likely to produce subpar work, the system as a whole contributes to the gap's widening. India's educational system is rife with access, completion, and quality disparities. In India, a child's educational experience is influenced by a variety of variables, including class, linguistic heritage, gender, race etc. These factors contribute to educational disparities in Indian society. This research paper examines the educational inequalities in India, factors contributing to educational inequality and the key features of NEP 2020 in providing equal educational opportunities to all for inclusive growth.

Keywords - Educational inequalities, NEP 2020, Right to Education Act, Gender Inequality, regional disparities,

Introduction –

India, a developing nation, has had to overcome a number of challenges in order to achieve growth. A crucial component of the development is education. Education is important for enhancing the general condition of a developing nation. When we consider the impact of education on India's development over time, several factors come into play. The few factors that contribute to inequality are regional differences, gender, caste, parental income, and occupation. Education Despite years of policymaking intended to bring about change, the term "inequality" is still widely used in India. Inequality is not seriously addressed in any way. It is past time for the Indian government and those who make educational policies to

acknowledge the seriousness of the situation. (2011, Kaushik and Ramani). To make education more efficient, it is essential to recognize the root causes of inefficiency.

The goal of govt and policy makers should be to list all of the obstacles that are preventing India from achieving universal education. India still has a low level of literacy among its population even after so many years of independence. It is crucial that India's economy makes the necessary advancements in order to compete with the economies of industrialized nations around the world. Education is a fundamental right for every child, regardless of their background, social status, or economic condition. India's education system is plagued by a significant gap in the quality and access to education, leading to widespread educational inequality. We will try to understand the various factors contributing to educational inequality in India and their impact on society.

Factors Contributing Educational Inequalities in India-

The Indian education system faces multiple challenges, including inadequate infrastructure, lack of quality teachers, and insufficient funding. These challenges disproportionately affect marginalized communities such as Dalits, Adivasis, Women, and Minority. Educational inequalities have far-reaching consequences for India's development. Firstly, they perpetuate poverty and income inequality. Education is a crucial tool for economic mobility, and those who are deprived of educational opportunities are likely to remain trapped in poverty. Secondly, educational inequalities hinder social mobility and perpetuate social inequality & injustice. Thirdly, educational inequalities limit the potential for scientific and technological progress, which is essential for India's overall growth and development. As a result, educational inequalities exist in different forms, including:

- **Access to Education:** Despite the Right to Education Act (RTE) 2009, which mandates free and compulsory education for all children between the ages of 6 and 14, many children in India still do not have access to education. According to the National Sample Survey of Estimation of Out-of-School (2014), only 56% of Indian children between the ages of 6 and 13 attend school. This figure is even lower among girls, children from low-income families, and those belonging to marginalized communities.
- **Quality of Education:** Even when children do have access to education, the quality of education they receive is often inadequate. The National Achievement Survey (NAS) 2017 found that only 47% of Class III students in government schools could read at the required level, and only 44% could perform basic math operations. This situation is worse in rural areas, where almost 70% of India's population lives.
- **Gender Inequality:** Gender-based educational inequalities are prevalent in India. Despite the constitutional guarantees of equality, gender discrimination remains a significant issue in Indian society. Female literacy rates in India are much lower than male literacy rates, The literacy rate (according to NSO survey 2017) for females is 70.3%, while for males it is 84.7%. The disparity is even more significant in rural areas, where cultural beliefs and practices like multiple barriers to education, including societal norms, child marriage, lack of safe transportation, and limited access to schools often discriminate against girls' education. These factors contribute

to lower enrolment rates and higher dropout rates among girls, particularly in rural areas.

- **Caste-based Inequalities:** India's caste system continues to play a significant role in determining access to education. The caste system, a hierarchical social structure deeply ingrained in Indian society, has perpetuated educational inequalities for centuries. Historically, individuals belonging to lower castes, such as Dalits (formerly known as Untouchables) and Adivasis (indigenous communities), have faced discrimination, exclusion, and limited access to educational opportunities. This discrimination and social exclusion continue to affect their educational outcomes and opportunities. According to NSS 75th round data, the literacy rate among scheduled tribes is only 69% and scheduled castes only 72%, compared to the national average of 74% (census 2011).
- **Socio-economic status:** One of the primary contributors to educational inequality in India is the socio-economic status of families. Children from lower-income families often face significant barriers to education, including lack of access to quality education, inadequate infrastructure, the need for child labor to support family income and limited access to quality schools and educational resources further perpetuates the cycle of poverty and educational disadvantage, and insufficient resources. According to the National Sample Survey (2014), only 53% of rural children attend school regularly, while the figure for urban children is 80%.
- **Regional disparities:** Education levels vary significantly across different regions of India. While some states have made significant progress in improving access and quality of education, others lag behind. Remote and economically disadvantaged regions, such as tribal areas and conflict-affected regions, often have limited infrastructure, insufficient resources, and a lack of qualified teachers, resulting in poor educational outcomes for the residents. According to a report by the National Sample Survey (NSO 2017), the literacy rate in Kerala is 96%, while in Bihar, it is only 70%. The differences are even more significant in terms of access to quality education, with urban areas and metro cities having better facilities than rural areas.
- **Language barrier:** India is a diverse country with many different languages spoken throughout the country. Lack of access to education in a child's native language can be a significant barrier to education, especially for children from rural areas.

Covid-19's Impact on Educational Inequality

Two years after the country's schools were forced to close to combat the epidemic, India's educational system is at risk of becoming even more unequal as a result of the digital revolution. According to several reports and articles, exclusionary learning has caused the majority of children without internet access to experience distress, with some even considering self-harm. Schools and other educational institutions were closed in the wake of COVID-19. In India, there are some students who only go to school to get food. The excellent midday meal programme has assisted many kids who couldn't bring a lunch to get the nutrition they required to thrive, they brought food from home. When the epidemic first started, closing schools and converting to online education appeared inevitable, but it quickly became apparent that this choice ignores students without access to digital infrastructure, such as a digital device and the internet. The transition to online learning raises concerns

about its effects, including learning loss, an increase in school dropouts, child marriages, child labor, and malnutrition, as well as what preparations have been made to address these problems.

Government Initiatives:

The Indian government has recognized the importance of addressing educational inequalities and has implemented various policies and programs to promote equal access to education. The Right to Education Act (RTE) was enacted in 2009, guaranteeing free and compulsory education for children aged 6 to 14 years. Affirmative action policies, such as reservations for disadvantaged groups in educational institutions, have also been implemented to promote social inclusion.

Despite these initiatives, the persistent challenges of educational inequality in India require sustained efforts and multi-faceted approaches. Improving infrastructure, enhancing teacher training and recruitment, addressing social biases and discrimination, promoting gender equality, and targeting resources to disadvantaged regions and communities are crucial steps to reduce educational inequalities and ensure a more equitable education system in India.

Annual Status of Education Report (ASER) 2022-

Despite the above-explained scenario ASER 2022, represents a positive picture of education with the help of some facts and figures:

- For the past 15 years, the enrolment rate for students between the ages of 6 and 14 has exceeded 95%. Despite the pandemic-related closure of some schools, overall enrollment increased from 97.2% in 2018 to 98.4% in 2022.
- From 2006 to 2014, the percentage of kids (aged 6 to 14) enrolled in government schools decreased steadily. This percentage was 64.9% in 2014, and it did not change significantly over the ensuing four years. However, from 65.6% in 2018 to 72.9% in 2022, the percentage of kids (ages 6 to 14) enrolled in government schools increased significantly. In nearly every state across the nation, government school enrollment is rising.
- In 2006, the all-India figure for the proportion of girls aged 11 to 14 who were not enrolled was 10.3%; over the subsequent ten years, this figure decreased to 4.1% in 2018. This percentage has decreased over time. The percentage of 11–14-year-old girls in India who are not enrolled in school in 2022 currently is 2%. Only in Uttar Pradesh does this number hover around 4%; in all other states, it is lower.
- Among older girls between the ages of 15 and 16, the decline in the percentage of girls who are not enrolled in school is even more pronounced. More than 20% of girls in the 15–16 age range were not enrolled in school nationally in 2008. In 2018, ten years later, this number dropped to 13.5%. Girls between the ages of 15 and 16 who are not enrolled have decreased over time, and their percentage was 7.9% in 2022. More than 10% of girls in this age group are not enrolled in school in only 3 states: Madhya Pradesh (17%), Uttar Pradesh (15%), and Chhattisgarh (11.2%).
- The percentage of 3-year-olds in rural India who are enrolled in some type of early childhood education is expected to reach 78.3% in 2022, an increase of 7.1 percentage points from levels in 2018. There has been a significant change in the enrollment

patterns of young children in the age range of 3 to 5 years who have transferred from other preschool and school systems to the ICDS (Anganwadi) system. As opposed to 57.1% in 2018, 66.8% of 3-year-olds were enrolled in Anganwadi Centres in 2022. Anganwadi enrollment among 4-year-olds increased from 50.5% in 2018 to 61.2% in 2022.

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020-

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 is a comprehensive policy framework that aims to transform the education system in India and address some of the critical issues contributing to educational inequality. This is India's third policy, which replaces the 1986 NEP. According to the government, the NEP 2020 was developed after taking into account over 2 lakh suggestions from various levels with the goal of comprehensive productivity and contributing citizens for building an equitable, inclusive, and plural society with a GER of 50% by 2035. The National Education Policy, 2020, has conveyed the structural change in the education system that aims to make India more competitive. The NEP proposes various reforms that could help remove educational inequality in India. Some of the roles of the NEP in removing educational inequality are:

- **Access to Education:** The NEP aims to provide universal access to education for all children in India, with a focus on disadvantaged groups. The policy proposes to increase the enrollment rate in schools and promote equitable access to education across all regions and socioeconomic groups.
- **Teacher Training:** The NEP emphasizes the need for quality teacher training and professional development, which can improve the quality of education imparted to students. The policy recommends setting up a National Mission for Mentoring, which will provide teachers with mentoring and support to enhance their skills and knowledge.
- **Curriculum Reforms:** The NEP proposes a new curriculum framework that focuses on promoting critical thinking, problem-solving, and creativity among students. The curriculum also emphasizes the development of skills such as communication, teamwork, and digital literacy, which can help students succeed in the 21st-century economy.
- **Technology-Enabled Learning:** The NEP recognizes the importance of technology in education and proposes to leverage it to improve access to education, promote personalized learning, and enhance the quality of education imparted to students. The policy recommends setting up a National Educational Technology Forum, which will provide a platform for educators to share best practices and collaborate on technology-enabled learning.
- **Multilingual Education:** The NEP recognizes the importance of multilingualism in education and proposes to promote education in the mother tongue or regional language of students. This can help overcome language barriers and improve access to education for marginalized communities.
- **Inclusion of Skill Development Courses:** Another emphasis has been placed on teaching students life skills when they finish school so that they can be self-sufficient. By incorporating contemporary subjects, vocational courses, and extracurricular activities from the school level, students will be drawn back to their schools. "Bal

Bhavans" will be established as a special daytime boarding school to provide support mechanisms tailored to their needs and to encourage students to participate in art-related, career-related, and play-related activities.

- **SEDGs (Socio-Economically Disadvantaged Groups):** The NEP 2020 acknowledges that certain groups are vastly underrepresented in current educational systems. The NEP has combined gender identities, socio-cultural identities, geographical identities, disabilities, and socio-economic conditions to form a new social group known as SEDGs in order to specifically address their educational needs. The majority of the policy's goals revolve around fostering inclusivity among these groups. As previously stated, these groups have higher dropout rates for a variety of reasons, ranging from lack of accessibility for tribal communities (geographic) to historical exclusion of communities from educational systems for the socio-cultural identities categorization. Recognising their unique needs, the NEP 2020 proposes a series of policies and programmes such as targeted scholarships, conditional cash transfers to incentivize parents to send their children to school, and providing bicycles for transportation, which have previously been shown to increase enrollment and create more representation.
- **Recognising gender identities:** The NEP 2020 recognises that female and transgender people are the most affected across all groups and socioeconomic categories. There are plans to implement schemes such as distributing bicycles to form cycling groups and establishing walking groups in schools to encourage community participation and create safety nets for these vulnerable students. Recognising the critical need for girl child education, the new policy proposes the establishment of a 'Gender-Inclusion Fund' to create better educational spaces for women and transgender people. The fund will be available to states in order for them to develop systems that will aid in the inclusion of these students.

NEP 2020 includes research capabilities and output across disciplines. Only high-quality interdisciplinary research across fields can address societal challenges, and the world's best research has occurred only in multidisciplinary educational institutions. The most recent groundbreaking event in India was the inclusion of the Right to Education in the Constitution under Article 32 A. The Indian Constitution provides for free and compulsory education for all children aged 6 to 14, but providing education to all remains a distant goal to this day. Education has never been a criterion for voting rights because anyone over the age of 18 can vote, whether literate or illiterate.

The New National Education Policy, 2020, which talks about sustainable human development and universal education learning with equity and learning outcomes with a research-oriented mindset, has provided a ray of hope as the cornerstone of all educational decisions. India has always placed education at the centre of its development agenda, and by bridging gender, social, and regional gaps through community participation, it will raise the spirits of all while ensuring equity in this policy. It will be a beautiful blend of both ancient and modern knowledge systems that will not only instill knowledge in you but will also aid in the integration of Indian culture and ethos.

In conclusion, the NEP has an essential role in removing educational inequality in India. The policy proposes various reforms that can address some of the critical issues contributing to

educational inequality, including access to education, teacher training, curriculum reforms, technology-enabled learning, and multilingual education. However, more needs to be done to ensure that all children in India have equal access to quality education. This requires addressing the root causes of educational inequalities, including poverty, discrimination, and social norms. By doing so, India can unlock the full potential of its people and achieve sustainable development. Implementing these reforms and proper implementation of NEP 2020 will require significant resources, political will, and collaboration between stakeholders, but it is a crucial step towards creating a more equitable and just education system in India.

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